

Q1 - "I agree to answer this survey, part of the European research project EcoBulk. It is clear to me that my answers are anonymous and I will not be asked to share any personal information"

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
"I agree to answer this survey, part of the European research project EcoBulk. It is clear to me that my answers are anonymous and I will not be asked to share any personal information"	1	1	1	0	0	3

Field	Choice Count
Yes	3
No	0
Total	3

Q4 - In your work, how aware or concerned are you of the following? (1 = Not aware nor concerned at all; 2 = Somewhat aware or concerned; 3 = Well aware or concerned)

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
Waste management/disposal	3	3	3	0	0	3
Pollution by single use plastics	2	3	2	0	0	3
Recycling of plastics	2	3	3	1	0	2
Recycling of large bulky waste (e.g. from construction)	2	3	2	0	0	3
Recycling of composite materials (glass fibre, carbon fibre, others)	2	3	3	0	0	3
Reuse and repurposing of products	2	3	2	0	0	3

Field	1	2	3	Total
Waste management/disposal	0	0	3	3
Pollution by single use plastics	0	2	1	3
Recycling of plastics	0	1	1	2

Recycling of large bulky waste (e.g. from construction)	0	2	1	3
Recycling of composite materials (glass fibre, carbon fibre, others)	0	1	2	3
Reuse and repurposing of products	0	2	1	3

Q5 - For each of the following statements, select whether you Agree, Neither agree or disagree, or Disagree.

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
The UK as a whole generates too much waste	1	2	1	0	0	3
Your place of work generates too much waste	1	3	2	1	1	3
Your place of work makes efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more	1	2	1	0	0	3
Your household generates too much waste	1	2	2	0	0	3
Your household makes efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more	1	1	1	0	0	3

Field	Agree	Neither agree or disagree	Disagree	Total
The UK as a whole generates too much waste	2	1	0	3
Your place of work generates too much waste	1	1	1	3
Your place of work makes efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more	2	1	0	3
Your household generates too much waste	1	2	0	3
Your household makes efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more	3	0	0	3

Q6 - For these materials, select those that you think must have mainstream municipal recycling capabilities

Field	Choice Count
Steel	2
Aluminium	2
Glass	2
Soft plastic (plastics that can be scrunched)	1
Composite materials (glass fibre, carbon fibre, others)	2
Hard plastic (plastics that can't be scrunched)	1
Paper/wood/cardboard	2
Textiles	1
Other	0
Total	13

Other - Text

Q13 - When choosing between two different products/supplier, how likely is it that sustainability factors would affect your decision?

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
When choosing between two different products/supplier, how likely is it that sustainability factors would affect your decision?	1	3	2	1	1	3

Field	Choice Count
Very likely	1
Likely	1
Equally likely	1
Unlikely	0
Very unlikely	0
It is irrelevant	0
Total	3

Q8 - In your work, does a product containing recycled material prevent you from buying, renting or leasing it?

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
In your work, does a product containing recycled material prevent you from buying, renting or leasing it?	1	3	2	1	1	3

Field	Choice Count
Yes	1
Sometimes or maybe	0
No	2
No opinion	0
Total	3

Q9 - If yes, maybe or sometimes, why? (Several answers possible)

Field	Choice Count
Inferior quality of the product	1
Less appealing look of the product	0
Difficulties to find such products	0
Lack of information about the proportion of recycled content	0
Inferior lifespan	0
Never thought about this	0
Other	0
Total	1

Other - Text

Q10 - Which product categories would you be likely to buy, rent or lease knowing that they contain recycled materials? (Select more than one if applicable)

Field	Choice Count
Clothing (e.g. work trousers or shoes)	2
Tools and electronics	2
Vehicle parts / equipment	1
Construction material	1
Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)	1
Other	0
Consumables	2
Total	9

Other - Text

Q16 - In your work, if you were to buy, rent or lease any product containing recycled material, which of the following would you find to be the most important aspect, when compared with those without any recycled material?

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
In your work, if you were to buy, rent or lease any product containing recycled material, which of the following would you find to be the most important aspect, when compared with those without any recycled material? - Selected Choice	2	5	4	1	2	3

Field	Choice Count
That the quality of the product with recycled material is the same or higher	1
That the cost of the product with recycled material is the same or lower	1
That no additional training is required to handle the product with recycled material	1
That no additional tools/consumables are required to handle the product with recycled material	0
Other	0
Total	3

Other - Text

Q17 - Does knowing that the material used for the construction of the shelter and furniture at the University of Warwick contains recycled materials make their "image" Better, Similar or Worse?

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
Does knowing that the material used for the construction of the shelter and furniture at the University of Warwick contains recycled materials make their "image" Better, Similar or Worse?	1	6	4	2	6	3

Field	Choice Count
Better	1
Similar	0
Worse	0
No opinion	2
Total	3

Q18 - About the material used in the shelters and furniture, select whether you Agree, Neither agree or disagree, Disagree.

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
It was easy to work with	1	3	2	1	1	3
It was similar to working with wood	2	3	2	0	0	3
The machines and tools used for traditional materials worked well with it	1	2	1	0	0	3
It was easy to make joints with it	1	3	2	1	1	3
You would not mind working with similar materials in the future	1	2	1	0	0	3

Field	Agree	Neither agree or disagree	Disagree	Total
It was easy to work with	2	0	1	3
It was similar to working with wood	0	2	1	3
The machines and tools used for traditional materials worked well with it	2	1	0	3
It was easy to make joints with it	1	1	1	3
You would not mind working with similar materials in the future	2	1	0	3